

SELECTION OF RESERVE ATHLETES FOR THE PARALYMPICS
ACCORDING TO THEIR KINEMATIC AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS
AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SPECIAL PROGRAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7475736>

Abstract. According to the analysis of the study, although scientific research has been carried out on the training of para-athletes, we can see that the boundaries of knowledge necessary for the selection of paralympic reserve athletes according to their kinematic and biochemical characteristics have not been expanded. Taking into account the growing demand for para-athletic athletes, the necessary and selected exercises for the training process, special equipment for knowing and studying the position levels of the athlete's bending and turning angles, modern innovative devices for studying and analyzing the kinematic and biochemical movement analysis of athletes, and literature, priority tasks, such as the implementation of measures aimed at providing methodical manuals, increase the urgency of the work.

Key words: Adaptive and developmental exercises, biochemical descriptions, special trainer, socio-pedagogical importance, general and special training, technical and tactical recommendations.

ОТБОР СПОРТСМЕНОВ РЕЗЕРВА НА ПАРАЛИМПИЙСКИЕ ИГРЫ ПО ИХ
КИНЕМАТИЧЕСКИМ И БИОХИМИЧЕСКИМ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАМ И
РАЗРАБОТКА СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ПРОГРАММЫ

Аннотация. Согласно анализу исследования, хотя и проводились научные исследования подготовки параспортсменов, мы видим, что границы знаний, необходимых для отбора спортсменов паралимпийского резерва по их кинематическим и биохимическим характеристикам, не расширились. С учетом растущего спроса у спортсменов-параспортсменов необходимые и подобранные упражнения для тренировочного процесса, специальное оборудование для познания и изучения позиционных уровней углов сгибания и поворота спортсмена, современные инновационные приборы для изучения и анализа кинематических и биохимических Анализ движений спортсменов и литературы, первоочередные задачи, такие как выполнение мероприятий, направленных на обеспечение методическими пособиями, повышают актуальность работы.

Ключевые слова: Адаптивно-развивающие упражнения, биохимические характеристики, специальный тренажер, социально-педагогическое значение, общая и специальная подготовка, технико-тактические рекомендации.

Introduction, A number of decisions aimed at the development of physical education and sports were made in our country. In particular, the President's decision No. PQ-5279 of November 5, 2021 "On measures to further increase the quality of the formation of the reserve of athletes in Olympic and Paralympic sports by fundamentally improving the sports education system" No. PQ-5114 of May 18, 2021 for the development of the field Decision "On Additional Measures for the Development of the Paralympic Movement", Decision No. PQ-414 dated November 3, 2022 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Training and Scientific Research" and other normative acts related to this field - assigns great responsibility to specialists in the field for the implementation of tasks defined in legal documents.

Today, many conditions have been created in our country to select people with limited physical abilities and disabilities, to direct and prepare them for sports, and many opportunities

are being created in order to achieve high results in sports. In particular, the fund of high achievements of para-athletic athletes, the practical task of developing new methods of training, the selection and orientation of more effective tools that increase the effectiveness of training activities are defined. At the same time, special attention is being paid to the creation of necessary conditions for sports activities for persons with limited physical abilities and disabilities, ensuring their appropriate participation in international sports arenas, and state support.

Much attention is being paid to measures related to solving specific problems of para-athletes, such as optimizing sports training and increasing the efficiency and reliability of sports activities. Nevertheless, development of the main directions of optimization of sports training of para-athletes is of urgent importance. The purpose and objectives of the research: development of proposals and descriptions for the optimization of sports training based on biomechanical indicators of para-athletes in mastering technical elements. In this: First, to expand the integrated management system of athletes due to the selection of means (on the basis of the muscles on which the main loads fall) and collective (physical qualities and techniques) control for each sport class of nosology based on the physical, technical, and functional condition of para-athletes' training; Secondly, in the technical training of para-athletic athletes, increasing the possibility of improving the sports results due to the speed of movement of the bending angles of the body in the sagittal plane compared to the initial phase of movement speed; Thirdly, optimization of the individual capabilities of para-athletic athletes due to timely correction of shoulder turns and deviations of body angles in relation to the body position, based on the biomechanical indicators of the technical movements of the para-athletic athletes in the technical reserve of the model characteristics;

Fourthly, optimization of sports practical training due to the development of microcycles that show great strength in a short period of time (quick strength, power, endurance) and by moderating weekly loads aimed at improving the explosive power of athletes using special equipment for exercises that require great strength in various trainings. In general, it involves the creation of a new model of interaction between science and practice in education, using the concept of innovative development of society. Among them are models of the innovative process characterized by scientific support integrated into a practical system. A special program is a special form of interaction between pedagogical sciences and practice in order to determine and experimentally verify the value of the latest achievements of pedagogical theory in the field of new educational content, forms and methods of proper organization of training, and methods of adequate management.

Our research is directly related to targeted changes in educational activities and evaluation of their consequences. The main novelty of our research is that the organization of innovative activities of athletes does not require the allocation of control and experimental groups, as it is aimed at establishing the compatibility of planned conditions and mechanisms for the construction of innovative educational practices. The scientific novelty of the research: The system of integrated management of athletes will be expanded due to the selection of means (on the basis of the muscles on which the main loads fall) and collective control (of their physical qualities and techniques) that can be performed for each sport class of the nosology based on the physical, technical, and functional state of training of para-athletes. ;

in the technical training of para-athletic athletes, the possibility of improving sports results increases due to the increase in the movement speed of the bending angles of the body in the sagittal, frontal plane; the individual capabilities of the athletes are optimized due to timely correction of the deviations of the shoulder turns, angular movements of the para-athletes based on the biomechanical indicators of the technical movements in the competition, the shortcomings of the model characteristics in relation to the body position; it is determined which sports type athletes can participate in, using special equipment for various exercises, and according to which

classification, guidelines are developed for each nosology, and programs are developed by standardizing weekly loads;

Tasks on kinematic and biochemical characteristics are solved in optimizing the training of disabled para-athletes. The analysis and methodology of the literature, the analysis of scientific-methodical literature on the topic shows that a number of our authors in our Republic are R.S.Salomov, M.Kh. Mirjamolov, L.B. Sobirova and other specialists have conducted various researches related to the field of prevention and treatment of stunting in elementary school students. A number of scientific works were carried out by leading scientists in the CIS countries, and I.V. Erkomayshvili, A. Sazonov, A.S. Solodkov and O.V. It was put into practice by Morozova et al.

Chow J.W., Kuenster A.F., Lim Y. on the classification of many types of injuries of the musculoskeletal system by foreign scientists in many countries of the world, on the age limits of the development of physical qualities and on the scientific methodical aspects of improving physical fitness MacLeish M.S., Cooper R.A. , Harralson J., Ster J.F. on the characteristics of improving sports performance. and various researches related to the field have been conducted by other experts. These circumstances encourage us to look for new approaches to optimizing the movement regime of para-athletes' injuries, affecting their motivational and emotional spheres, creating a strong interest in sports results in athletes and creating tools that have a positive effect on reducing movement deficits, and there is a need to substantiate their effectiveness in pedagogical experience.

The approach used in the research is based on the opinions of foreign and national scientists in the field of adaptive physical education and sports training theory and methodology, the use of complementary research methods suitable for the research tasks, the analysis and research tasks are provided in terms of quantity and quality, experimental testing It is explained by the re-development of the work and the obtained results with the help of mathematical and statistical analysis methods, and the confirmation of the results by the competent structures. Today, it is known to everyone that new modern technologies are entering the development of every industry. These tools are important for their efficiency, effectiveness and wide range of application. This project is also important because it focuses on improving the comprehensive training of para-athletes as a result of combining the possibilities of physical education and sports and computer technologies. selection and control of the means of training of athletes by sports, for each classification of nosology;

Improvement of technical preparation of para-athletes taking into account the angle of inclination and acceleration of the body while performing elements of technique; development of proposals and recommendations for optimization of individual capabilities of para-athletic athletes due to the correction of technical model characteristics of competition exercises; development of percussive microcycles aimed at the use of special equipment by highly skilled athletes. An innovative project based on kinematic and biochemical characteristics is developed to improve the complex (psychological, physical, functional) training of para-athletes with musculoskeletal injuries through special equipment, and to optimize training, and to create a special program and put it into practice.

Based on the above, kinematic and biochemical analyzes of para-athletes are studied through modern computer programs, and it is urgent to analyze and provide them with the physical training and technique of athletes through a special program. Specific methods are used to create a program for the use of special trainers. At the same time, together with the pedagogical methods of conducting research, the use of special computer programs, their application and the processes of determining their effectiveness are also carried out. The scheme of creating a special program and testing it in practice is shown as follows.

1. Sport classifications of persons with disabilities are defined according to nasology. There are 10 types of disabilities, 8 of which are physically impaired, visually impaired, and intellectually impaired.

2. Paralympic reserve athletes are taught to be divided into sports corresponding to their classification. Para athletics; T/F, para powerlifting; A1-A4, barrel; BC1-BC4, para cycling; T1-T2, C1-C5, para volleyball; VS1-VS2, goalball; B1-B3, para table tennis; sport class from 1-10, para taekwondo; K41-K44, para swimming; SM1-SM10, para shooting; SH1-SH2, para judo; J1,J2, para canoe; KL1, KL2, KL3, wheelchair fencing; 1A-1B, soccer 5x5; Sports classes B1-B3 are approved

3. Test criteria specific to sports and classifications of para-athletes are developed and selected based on this.

Жисмоний имконияти чеklangан пара спортчиларни МЖТ ва УЖТ бўйича меъёрий талаблари ва баҳолаш мезонлари. (оёқ нозологияси) (ўғил болалар учун)

МЖТ		УЖТ			
3 кг тўлдирма тўпни бош орқасидан улоктириш (см) 93 балл		Турникда тортилиш (марта) 32 балл		Қўшпояда тирсакни букиб ёзиш (марта) 31 балл	
Натижа	Балл	Натижа	Балл	Натижа	Балл
8.81-9.00	93	18	32	39-40	31
8.61-8.80	90	17	30	37-38	30
8.41-8.60	87	16	28	35-36	29
8.21-8.40	84	15	26	33-34	28
8.01-8.20	81	14	24	31-32	27
7.81-8.00	78	13	22	29-30	26
7.61-7.80	74	12	20	27-28	25
7.41-7.60	71	11	18	25-26	24
7.21-7.40	68	10	16	23-24	23
7.01-7.20	65	9	14	21-22	22
6.81-7.00	62	8	12	19-20	21
6.61-6.80	59	7	10	18	20
6.41-6.60	56	6	8	17	19
6.21-6.40	53	5	6	16	18
6.01-6.20	50	4	4	15	17
5.81-6.00	47	3	3	14	16
5.61-5.80	44	2	2	13	15

4. Conducting a kinematic analysis on the equipment (h/p/cosmos® pulsar® 3p) for preparing reserve athletes for the Paralympics, developing a module description of the athlete and giving recommendations on achievements and shortcomings.

5. Biochemical analysis of para-athletes is carried out on the Darppon ES-101C equipment. This equipment allows biochemical analyzers to analyze plasma and blood serum according to a number of indicators: the content of specific proteins, enzymes, substrates, lipids, electrolytes, and the obtained results allow to assess the state of various organ systems.

6. Special programs will be developed for the training of Paralympic reserve athletes, corresponding to their sports, nosology and para sports classifications. There are 22 sports in the programs of the Paralympics, and only 7 of these sports are developing in our country, therefore, the special program developed by us includes para athletics, para powerlifting, para taekwondo, para swimming, para shooting, para judo, para canoe sports. (if sports wheelchairs and sports prostheses are brought to increase the number of sports, at least 15-16 para sports will be developed in our country)

7. When preparing para - athletes for the sports reserve, skill classes for using modern simulators for sports are shown. Methodological instructions are developed for the rational and correct use of these simulators

8. Preparation of para-athletes for the sports reserve and educational processes on a special program for sports are organized. For all sports schools, specialized schools, training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports, UzDJTSU Nukus and Fergana branches in our republic.

9. All educational institutions and organizations in the field of adaptive sports will be provided with handouts, methodological manuals, training manuals, textbooks and programs created for para sports. Our republic has 254 sports schools, 56 specialized schools, 14 training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports, branches of UzDJTSU Nukus and Fergana.

The created special program allows to determine the possibility of increasing the physical complex training of athletes with disabilities, as well as to determine the analysis of improving movement skills of athletes, as well as to determine their biochemical characteristics. Assessing the kinematic indicators of disabled athletes, studying their shortcomings in performing 3600 movement techniques and improving their mechanisms; is to expand the possibility of para

athletes to achieve high results in international competitions due to the study of model indicators of highly qualified athletes and the use of model indicators of turning and bending angles of athletes. At the same time, it will be possible to give scientific-methodical suggestions and recommendations regarding the description and application of the possibilities of this mechanism.

In conclusion, sports classifications of persons with disabilities according to nosology are defined and athletes are divided into sports types that correspond to the classifications. Coaches and athletes are given insights and test norms specific to sports and classifications of para-athletes are developed and sorted based on this. In order to achieve high results of para-athletes, kinematic analysis is carried out on the equipment (h/p/cosmos® pulsar® 3p) and a module description of the athlete is developed, recommendations are made on achievements and shortcomings, and the equipment (Darppon ES-101C) is used for biochemical analysis of para-athletes.

This equipment allows biochemical analyzers to analyze plasma and blood serum according to a number of indicators: the content of specific proteins, enzymes, substrates, lipids, electrolytes, and the obtained results allow to assess the state of various organ systems. In order to optimize the training loads of the Paralympic reserve athletes, skill classes are organized using modern simulators, which are suitable for their sports, nosology and classification of para sports. Preparation of para-athletes for the sports reserve and educational processes according to a special program for sports are organized, guidelines for adaptive sports are developed and scientific and methodological literature is created. Testing and implementation of the results: will be discussed at the State University of Physical Education and Sports of Uzbekistan, and special innovative programs will be developed based on the research results. Publication of scientific results: The relevant documents for intellectual property objects are obtained for research results. Scientific articles are published in prestigious scientific journals and journals indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus databases.

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